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AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the comprehensive Dissemination and Communication Plan for the PLIADES project, corresponding to T8.1: Dissemination Plan and Marketing & Promotional Material activities. The primary goal of this plan is to ensure the effective dissemination and communication of the project's progress, results, and impacts to a broad range of stakeholders, including technology and services providers, system or platform integrators, academia, policymakers, and the general public.

The PLIADES Dissemination and Communication Plan is designed to effectively share the project's innovations and outcomes with a diverse range of stakeholders. By strategically leveraging multiple channels and activities, the plan aims to maximise the project's visibility, impact, and adoption, ultimately contributing to the project's success and long-term sustainability.

This comprehensive plan includes tailored communication strategies, activities, and tools to engage different target audiences. Additionally, it establishes specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of dissemination efforts.

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List of Terms and Definitions

Table 1. Definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
D&E&C	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

Preface

The PLIADES Dissemination and Communication Plan is designed to effectively share the project's innovations and outcomes with a diverse range of stakeholders.

The dissemination and communication strategy for PLIADES aims to:

- Increase awareness of the project's objectives, methodologies, and outcomes among targeted stakeholders, including policymakers, industry professionals, academic researchers, and the general public.
- Build and maintain effective communication channels to ensure stakeholders are informed and engaged with the project's progress and developments.
- Maximise the visibility and accessibility of PLIADES project activities and outcomes to its community and target audiences.
- Foster the adoption and practical application of PLIADES' innovations and findings by stakeholders in real-world scenarios.
- Develop strategies to ensure the long-term impact and scalability of PLIADES outcomes beyond the project's duration, ensuring sustained benefit and influence.

The dissemination strategy leverages a variety of channels and activities, each tailored to effectively reach specific target audiences, including but not limited to marketing pack and promotional press kit, project identity and branding, press releases, newsletters, social media, short videos, web/ social content, articles, workshops/ conferences/ demonstrations, publications etc.

To ensure the effectiveness of the dissemination and communication activities, specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been defined for each channel. These KPIs include targets for brochure downloads, conference participation, industry links, event attendance, training sessions, publication outputs, social media interactions, and more. Regular monitoring and evaluation of these KPIs will allow the PLIADES team to adjust strategies and tactics to maximise impact.

The adoption of dissemination tools and activities will be guided by a defined checklist to ensure alignment with PLIADES's objectives. Key considerations include the relevance of the content, target audience, intended impact, communication style, accessibility, and compliance with confidentiality and funding acknowledgment requirements.

The PLIADES Dissemination and Communication Plan aims to enhance project visibility, impact, and long-term sustainability through strategic dissemination efforts.

1 Introduction

1.1 Objective and Scope

This deliverable describes the dissemination plan for the PLIADES project, detailing the steps to be taken throughout the project's life cycle to maximise its impact and reach relevant audiences. It encompasses the project's dissemination goals, target groups, dissemination channels, and execution plan. Additionally, it aims to guide PLIADES project partners on effective dissemination of all project-related information and reporting on their communication and dissemination activities. The document includes a list of dissemination materials and useful templates for the project partners.

Successful dissemination requires implementation by all partners to ensure that all relevant communities are reached, not just those of a designated "dissemination partner". The deliverable follows a continuous improvement cycle based on the Plan - Do - Check - Act approach and will be updated annually to include necessary adjustments and communication reports.

1.2 Document Structure

This document is structured to provide a clear and systematic approach to dissemination and communication activities within the PLIADES project. It comprises the following sections:

- Section 2: Dissemination Strategy - Outlines the objectives and strategic approach for dissemination and stakeholder engagement.
- Section 3: Dissemination channels and activities - Describes the tools and channels to be used for dissemination activities, including the project logo, website, press releases, leaflets, posters, factsheets, presentations, social media, newsletters, workshops, short videos, conference participation, and scientific publications.
- Section 4: Execution Plan - Details the rules, guidelines, and planned activities for the project's dissemination efforts from M1 to M36.
- Section 5: Monitoring - Provides the indicators and metrics for monitoring the effectiveness of the dissemination activities and the achievement of the set objectives.

1.3 Reference Documents

The following reference documents are essential for understanding the framework and guidelines used in the PLIADES dissemination and communication plan:

- PLIADES Grant Agreement
- Horizon Europe Programme Guidelines
- European Commission's Communication and Dissemination Guidelines

2 Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Objectives

The dissemination strategy for the PLIADES project is designed to maximise the impact of the project's results by effectively communicating its objectives, activities, and outcomes to a diverse audience. The strategy aims to ensure that the knowledge generated by the project is shared widely and utilised by stakeholders, thereby enhancing the project's overall impact and sustainability. The following specific objectives guide the dissemination efforts. In this regard, the following specific objectives guide the dissemination efforts:

- **Identify and engage key stakeholders:** To build a comprehensive stakeholder network, ensuring that all relevant parties are informed about and involved in the project from an early stage.
- **Promote awareness and understanding:** To increase awareness and understanding of the project's goals, methodologies, and results among targeted audiences, including policymakers, industry professionals, academic researchers, and the general public.
- **Establish and continuously update dissemination channels:** To create and maintain effective communication channels for sharing project information and results, ensuring that stakeholders are kept up-to-date with the latest developments.
- **Enhance visibility and accessibility:** To promote the visibility and accessibility of the project's activities and outcomes to the PLIADES community and target audiences, thereby maximising the project's reach and impact.
- **Facilitate the exploitation of project outcomes:** To ensure that the project's findings and innovations are accessible and utilised by stakeholders, fostering the adoption and application of PLIADES' results in real-world scenarios.
- **Ensure sustainability and scalability:** To create a sustainable impact by developing strategies for the long-term use and scalability of the project's outcomes beyond the project's lifecycle, ensuring ongoing benefit and influence.

2.2 Strategic Approach

To ensure the broad span and effective reach of all target stakeholders, all PLIADES project partners will be involved in the planned Dissemination and Communication (D&C) activities. These activities will be led by Hypertech, a partner with extensive experience in digital marketing and communication services. Hypertech will ensure that the PLIADES activities and outcomes are widely disseminated among the identified target audiences in a timely manner and through appropriate methods.

The dissemination and communication strategy of the PLIADES project comprises the following main features:

- **Maintain an Ambitious and Cohesive Vision:** This involves clearly defining the project's scope, expected results, desired usability, and targeted audience. By maintaining a cohesive vision, the project can ensure all stakeholders are aligned and understand the project's objectives and potential impact.
- **Ensure Value Delivery to Stakeholders:** The strategy aims to deliver value to stakeholders effectively and efficiently. This includes providing relevant and timely information, updates, and results that stakeholders can use to enhance their understanding and application of the PLIADES framework.
- **Build Upon Strong and Cohesive Teamwork:** Effective teamwork among all partners is crucial for the success of the dissemination and communication activities. By fostering a collaborative

environment, the project can leverage the strengths and expertise of all partners to maximise the impact of the D&C efforts.

These guiding principles will be achieved by ensuring continuity in the selected activities actively pursued by the partners in related areas. Additionally, a cohesive plan of action will be provided, utilising a variety of powerful instruments to stimulate impact and engagement.

The strategic approach for the dissemination and communication (D&C) plan of the PLIADES project is designed to ensure a broad and lasting impact by engaging a wide range of stakeholders and effectively conveying the project's objectives, methodologies, and outcomes. This approach is structured into three main phases, each tailored to different stages of the project lifecycle to maximise reach and engagement.

Table 2. Strategic phases for the D&C plan of the PLIADES project

Phase	Focus/Target/Aim	Actions
Phase I (Year 1)	Building Awareness	The first phase focuses on raising awareness and interest among key stakeholders. This involves developing a strong visual identity for the project, including a logo, templates, and branding materials, which will be consistently used across all dissemination channels. A project website will be launched, serving as the central hub for all information related to PLIADES. During this phase, tailored dissemination and communication materials such as brochures, leaflets, factsheets and posters will be created and distributed. Social media channels will be established to facilitate broader engagement and interaction with the public.
Phase II (Years 2-3)	Reinforcing Impact	In the second phase, the focus shifts to reinforcing the project's impact through targeted dissemination of Key Exploitable Results (KERs). This phase aims to showcase the benefits of the PLIADES framework and support its future exploitation. Activities will include publishing scientific papers in peer-reviewed journals, presenting at international conferences, and participating in industry fairs and workshops. The project team will actively engage with stakeholders through webinars, training sessions, and demonstration events, promoting knowledge exchange and fostering collaboration. Efforts will be made to establish and strengthen links with relevant EU communities and projects, creating synergies that enhance the dissemination impact.
Phase III (Year 4 and beyond)	Fostering Uptake and Replication	The final phase focuses on promoting the uptake and replication of the project's results beyond its lifespan. This involves extensive dissemination of the final KERs, business models, and outcomes to a wider audience, including new data spaces. The goal is to create a fertile ecosystem that supports the scalability and sustainability of the PLIADES framework. During this phase, the project will continue to engage with stakeholders through various channels, including technical publications, presentations, and collaborations with industry partners. Special emphasis will be placed on showcasing success stories and case studies to demonstrate the practical benefits and adaptability of the PLIADES solutions.

Throughout the project’s implementation, all digital and online channels will be utilised, as detailed in the following sections. The project’s website and social media channels will play a pivotal role in raising awareness and disseminating the project’s results and expected impact. Furthermore, synergies with similar initiatives will be enforced and strengthened through the use of every deployed digital tool, ensuring the focus remains on results and effectively reaching the identified target audience.

2.3 Identification of Stakeholders & Engagement Strategy

Involving all relevant stakeholders is crucial for any project to be successful. One of the primary tasks of PLIADES is to define and agree upon stakeholder categories that will provide an initial point of reference for the dissemination strategy. However, these categories may be updated and redefined as the project progresses.

The project plan includes various activities aimed at disseminating information. A critical task is to identify specific stakeholders, categorise them into different groups, and analyse what motivates their interest in the project.

The first step in the stakeholder engagement strategy is the identification of key stakeholders who have a vested interest in the PLIADES project. These stakeholders are categorised into several groups:

Table 3. Key stakeholder groups, motivations, and target audiences for the PLIADES project

Stakeholder group	Why we want to reach this stakeholder group	Identified Stakeholders/ Target Groups
Data Spaces Ecosystems	This group includes stakeholders from various sectors such as mobility, energy, industrial, Green Deal, and healthcare. Reaching these ecosystems is crucial for the success of PLIADES, as they are the primary beneficiaries of the project's framework.	TECNALIA (industrial sector), VICOMTECH (mobility sector), EURECAT (healthcare sector), and academia partners involved in the Green Deal.
Technology and Services Providers	These stakeholders are essential for the dissemination and exploitation of PLIADES' technological solutions. Engaging with them can open new business and investment opportunities, fostering innovative approaches.	Government bodies and relevant tech companies such as T-Systems (Germany), Indra (Spain), and Telecom Italia (Italy).
System or Platform Integrators	These stakeholders will support the dissemination of technological and procedural results, promoting the PLIADES framework's scalability and adaptability.	Major tech firms like Google Cloud, AWS, Microsoft Azure, and digital transformation partners like CapGemini and NTT Data.
Policy-Making Bodies and Governance	Engaging with policy-making bodies ensures alignment with regulatory frameworks and contributes to the development of EU policies and directives.	Organisations such as OECD (France), European Board for Data Protection (Belgium), and national supervisory authorities like the Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (Spain).
EU Citizens - General Public, Scientific Community	The scientific community and general public are critical for expanding the project's reach and fostering further research and adoption of the PLIADES framework.	Academic institutions like Okayama University (Japan), RMIT (Australia), University of Eindhoven (Netherlands), and active European academic groups.

Achieving mutual understanding of the motivations and goals of each stakeholder group will be crucial before engaging in further collaboration, as each category has different motivations and interests regarding their involvement in the PLIADES project. This will enable effective planning, prioritisation, and high engagement from stakeholders who will be held accountable.

However, each stakeholder category also has a different level of influence over change, communication reach, or decision-making. In this regard, the PLIADES partnership will need to correctly identify the key players who can actively assist in making the project's objectives heard by crucial decision-making organisations or individuals.

By considering the two factors of interest and power, the project's dissemination methods will be adjusted throughout and beyond the implementation phase to target the appropriate stakeholders in each field of interest and at any given stage of the project.

Another crucial aspect is that different stakeholder groups may share motives or strategies, leading to potential synergies regarding technical or functional issues, and in planning the overall strategy for exploiting the project's results.

As part of the broader dissemination strategy, stakeholder engagement will be planned and executed in accordance with and based on feedback from the project's various communication activities. It will be based on the combination of interest, power, and timing of each contributing stakeholder group, enabling greater visibility and impact for the PLIADES project. Additionally, it will utilise all available tools and channels shared among all communication and dissemination activities implemented during the project.

The stakeholder engagement strategy is guided by the following objectives:

- **Building Awareness:** Ensure stakeholders are aware of PLIADES' objectives, activities, and potential benefits from the outset.
- **Collecting Feedback:** Gather valuable insights and feedback from stakeholders to refine and enhance the project's outcomes.
- **Promoting Collaboration:** Foster a collaborative environment where stakeholders actively contribute to and benefit from the project.
- **Facilitating Adoption:** Encourage stakeholders to adopt and integrate the project's results into their respective domains.
- **Ensuring Sustainability:** Develop long-term relationships with stakeholders to ensure the project's outcomes continue to have an impact beyond its lifecycle.

To achieve these objectives, the PLIADES project will implement a variety of tailored engagement activities across the different phases of the project.

Table 4. Stakeholder engagement strategy and implementation activities

Phase	Dissemination activities
Phase I: Building Awareness (Year 1)	Stakeholder Workshops: Organise introductory workshops to present the project's goals, scope, and potential impact to key stakeholders. These workshops will also serve as a mean for gathering initial feedback and understanding stakeholder expectations and requirements.
	Awareness Campaigns: Launch targeted awareness campaigns to disseminate information about PLIADES to a broader audience. This includes using newsletters, social media, and the project website to share updates and key information.
	Visual Identity Development: Develop a strong visual identity for the project by creating branded materials such as brochures, leaflets, factsheets and posters. These materials will ensure a consistent and

	<p>professional representation of the project across all dissemination channels.</p>
Phase II: Reinforcing Impact (Years 2-3)	<p>Scientific Publications and Presentations: Engage the scientific community and industry professionals by publishing results in high-impact journals and presenting findings at international conferences and workshops. This will highlight the project's contributions to the field and foster academic and professional interest.</p>
	<p>Pilot Demonstrations: Conduct live demonstrations of the PLIADES framework at relevant industry events and exhibitions. These demonstrations will showcase the practical applications and benefits of the project's innovations, driving interest and potential adoption.</p>
	<p>Stakeholder Feedback Sessions: Organise regular feedback sessions with key stakeholders to discuss the project's progress, gather input, and adjust strategies as needed. These sessions will ensure continuous stakeholder engagement and alignment with project goals.</p>
Phase III: Fostering Uptake and Replication (Year 4 and Beyond)	<p>Success Stories and Case Studies: Develop and disseminate detailed case studies and success stories to illustrate the effectiveness and scalability of PLIADES solutions. These materials will demonstrate the practical benefits and adaptability of the project's innovations to a wider audience.</p>
	<p>Long-term Collaborations: Establish long-term partnerships with key stakeholders to promote the ongoing use and development of the project's outcomes. These collaborations will help ensure the sustainability and scalability of the PLIADES framework beyond the project's lifespan.</p>
	<p>Policy Briefings and Reports: Prepare and distribute policy briefings and comprehensive reports to inform policymakers and regulatory bodies of the project's achievements and recommendations. This will facilitate the adoption of PLIADES innovations at a policy level.</p>

3 Dissemination channels and activities

According to dissemination strategy, as presented in the previous section, PLIADES strategic approach employs a multi-channel dissemination strategy to reach diverse stakeholders effectively. This includes:

- **Project Website and Social Media:** Maintaining an active online presence to engage with a broader audience.
- **Workshops and Demonstrations:** Organising and participating in various events, workshops, and conferences to engage with stakeholders in person and promote the project's results.
- **Publications and Conferences:** Disseminating scientific results through high-impact journals and conferences.
- **Collaborations:** Partnering with related projects and initiatives to leverage synergies and expand reach.

In this regard, the main tools identified to support the promotion of the project and its findings are illustrated in the following table:

Table 5. D&C tools for project promotion

Dissemination and Communication Support Tools and Channels	Objectives
Project Website	Central information point of the project.
Press Releases	Inform all relevant stakeholders about key activities and events of PLIADES.
Leaflet (Wider Audience)	Provide information about the project that anyone can easily carry.
Leaflet (Project Results)	Share detailed information about PLIADES project outcomes.
Poster	Offer a comprehensive and clear overview of PLIADES in a single page.
Factsheets	These will ensure that stakeholders are consistently informed about the project's status and impact.
Slide-based Presentation (Short/General)	Standard presentation that partners can adapt/translate according to their needs, objectives, and target audience.
Slide-based Presentation (Extended)	Extended presentation for more expert audiences that partners can adapt/translate according to their needs, objectives, and target audience.
Twitter Page	Increase awareness of PLIADES, highlighting key milestones and events.
LinkedIn Page	Increase awareness of PLIADES, marking key milestones and events.

YouTube Channel		Provide a centralised location for all PLIADES videos.
Newsletters		Keep stakeholders informed about PLIADES activities.
Short videos		Further promotion of the project will be achieved through appropriately prepared video material, which will be published regularly
Workshops/ Conferences/ Demonstrations	Organisation/ attendance to conferences/ workshops	Raise awareness of PLIADES through interactive sessions. Present the PLIADES' outcomes and attract more entities to widen network and dataspace ecosystems
	Open access exhibitions and demonstration events	Outreach nonspecialised audiences
	Onsite pilot promotional demonstrations/ workshops	Attract customers, raise awareness and disseminates PLIADES' demonstration results
	Online and/ or F2F training/ webinars	Ensure system operators understands benefits
Publications	Scientific Publications and Presentations/ Open access reports	Publish results in international scientific/technical literature and present at conferences, seminars, and workshops to engage the scientific community and industry professionals.
	Non-scientific reports	Adoption by industry
	Project Technical e- Publication	Collect relevant results in the form of data and observations, providing comprehensive evidence on the advantages of the PLIADES framework and lessons learned.
Synergies	Industry links, synergies	Attract other potential partners to work in collaboration with dataspace and their ecosystems
	Liaison with Relevant EU Communities and Collaboration with Relevant Projects	Seek liaison with EU communities and collaborate with other relevant projects to create synergies, complement activities, and disseminate results to a specialised audience.

3.1 Logo and templates

A strong visual identity is crucial for the successful dissemination and communication of the PLIADES project. To establish a consistent and recognisable brand, four alternative logo designs were created, as illustrated in the following figures.

Figure 1. Logo option 1

Figure 2. Logo option 2

Figure 3. Logo option 3

Figure 4. Logo option 4

These options were then presented to project partners for selection. The voting results for the logo options were as follows:

- Option 1: 24.2%
- Option 2: 21.2%
- Option 3: 9.1%
- Option 4: 45.5%

Option 4, which received the highest percentage of votes, has been selected as the official logo for the PLIADES project. This logo will be prominently used across all dissemination and communication materials, ensuring a cohesive and professional visual identity.

The PLIADES logo, selected from four proposed alternatives, features a distinct colour palette that underscores the project's innovative and technological focus. These colours have been carefully chosen to convey reliability, creativity, and clarity in all visual communications. The primary colours used in the logo are as follows:

Figure 5. PLIADES logo colour pallet

Figure 6. PLIADES logo in different backgrounds

In addition to the logo, a set of templates has been developed to ensure consistency in all project-related documents and presentations. These templates include:

- Document Templates (see Section 6.1): Templates for project reports, deliverables, and other official documents. These templates include the PLIADES logo, colour scheme, and designated sections to ensure a consistent format and appearance across all project documentation.
- PowerPoint Presentation Template (see Section 6.2): A standardized slide deck with the PLIADES logo and colour scheme, designed for use in all project presentations. This template will help maintain a uniform look and feel during workshops, conferences and other events.

This uniform branding will help enhance the project's visibility and recognition among stakeholders, reinforcing the professional and coordinated nature of the PLIADES project.

By implementing these visual identity elements, the PLIADES project aims to create a strong, recognisable brand that supports its dissemination and communication objectives, ensuring that the project's message is effectively conveyed to a broad audience.

3.2 Project Website

The PLIADES project website (<https://www.pliades-project.eu/>) serves as the central hub for all information related to the project, ensuring a cohesive and accessible platform for dissemination and communication. The website is designed to cater to a wide range of stakeholders, including policymakers, industry professionals, academic researchers, and the general public. It aims to provide comprehensive and up-to-date information on the project's objectives, progress, results, and impact.

At the beginning of the design process, a Sitemap (Figure 7) and a Figma prototype (Figure 8) were created to guide the development of the website and ensure a cohesive user experience.

Figure 7. PLIADES sitemap

Figure 8. Figma prototype of the PLIADES homepage

Key Features of the PLIADES website

1. **Homepage:** The homepage offers an overview of the PLIADES project, highlighting key aspects such as the project's goals, key objectives, news updates, and upcoming events. It is designed to capture the visitor's interest and provide easy navigation to other sections of the website. The primary purpose of the homepage is to provide basic information about the project, allowing visitors to quickly grasp what the project is about and become interested in exploring further. The homepage is vertically split into three conceptual parts: the upper part, the main part, and the footer part.

The upper part of the homepage is depicted in the figure below. The upper part includes the project logo, the top menu bar, the front-page slideshow, and a preview button for the project video. The top menu bar provides navigation to all sections of the project website. The slideshow features relevant images and the project's motto, e.g., "PLIADES - AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimisation and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability." Additionally, a button for previewing a featured project video is integrated, which opens a YouTube viewer to present the video.

Figure 9. Upper part of project homepage

Main Part: This part presents the project's key aim, approach, and vision, along with a news section. On the left-hand side, the latest news about the project is displayed, while on the right-hand side, a X widget shows the project's X timeline. This setup allows visitors to retrieve key information and stay updated on the latest news and tweets right from the homepage. There is also a horizontal scrolling carousel with the logos of project partners.

Figure 10. Main part of project homepage

Figure 11. Main part of project homepage

Footer Part: The footer contains the project disclaimer, the website map, and contact information. At the bottom, the website copyright appears, along with the project’s social media links and Privacy and Cookies policy.

Figure 12. Footer page

Since the website uses cookies to help navigation and comply with GDPR, a GDPR-compliant Cookie Consent Banner is used.

Figure 13. GDPR Cookie Consent Banner

- 2. Overview Section:** This section provides detailed information about the PLIADES project, including its background, excellence, vision, objectives and use cases.

Figure 14. Overview section

3. **Partners section:** This section introduces the consortium partners and their roles within the project, with a separate webpage for each partner.
4. **Media:** A repository of multimedia content, including brochures, banners, press releases, newsletters, photos and videos is available for stakeholders.

Figure 15. Media section

5. **Results:** This section houses all project-related public documents, including public deliverables, scientific publications, demos etc. All materials are accessible for download, promoting transparency and knowledge sharing.
6. **News:** Regular updates on project activities, milestones and results are posted in this section. It includes news articles, press releases, and blog posts to keep stakeholders informed about the latest project developments.

Figure 16. News section

7. **Contact Information:** The website includes a contact section with details on how to reach the project team for further information, collaboration inquiries, or feedback.

Figure 17. Contact page

The website is equipped with interactive features such as a newsletter subscription form, social media integration, and a contact form. These features enhance engagement and facilitate direct communication with stakeholders.

The PLIADES website is designed with user experience in mind, ensuring that it is easy to navigate, visually appealing, and responsive across different devices. The design incorporates the project's branding elements, including the logo and colour palette, to maintain a consistent visual identity.

Maintenance and Updates

The website is regularly maintained and updated by Hypertech's team to ensure that the content remains current and relevant. This includes adding new publications, updating event information, and posting news about project milestones.

3.3 Press Releases

Press releases will be issued to inform relevant stakeholders and the general public about key activities, milestones, and achievements. The press releases will be carefully crafted to ensure clarity, accuracy, and engagement, aiming to maximise the project's visibility and impact.

Each press release will contain the following key elements:

- **Headline:** A clear and engaging headline that captures the essence of the announcement.
- **Dateline:** The release date
- **Introduction:** A brief introduction summarising the key points of the press release.
- **Body:** Detailed information about the announcement, including the context, significance, and implications of the news.

- **Quotes:** Relevant quotes from key project members or stakeholders to add credibility and a human touch to the announcement.
- **Contact Information:** Details on how to reach the project team for further information.

They will be published on the website and sent to all relevant media and networks through the partners' mailing lists.

Press releases will be issued for various types of announcements, including but not limited to:

- **Project Launch:** Announcing the initiation of the PLIADES project, its objectives, and key partners.
- **Major Milestones:** Updates on significant project milestones, such as the completion of key phases or the achievement of important objectives.
- **Events:** Announcements of upcoming events, workshops, conferences, and webinars organised by the PLIADES project.
- **Results and Publications:** Dissemination of major project results, scientific publications, and other significant outcomes.

A first press release was made available for the project launch, as presented in Section 6.3.

3.4 Leaflets, Posters, Factsheets

Leaflets

Two types of leaflets will be made available to partners:

- **General Audience Leaflet:** This leaflet is designed for a broad audience and will be distributed at conferences, workshops, and within partner organisations. It has already been published (see section 6.4).
- **Project Outcomes Leaflet:** This leaflet will focus on the project's outcomes and results and will be prepared in the final six months of the project.

Both leaflets will include an abstract of the project that is accessible to non-specialists, such as the media and the general public. They are designed to be easily printable (maximum of two pages) and will be regularly updated to reflect the project's progress.

Posters

In addition to the leaflets, an A3 poster will be prepared. This poster will provide a visual overview of the project's objectives and outcomes, key messages, and a list of partners. It is intended for use at relevant events, workshops, and conferences. The poster will be extended and updated as needed throughout the project to incorporate the latest results.

Factsheets

The dissemination activities will also include the production and distribution of project factsheets, both interim and final. These factsheets will offer concise and accessible summaries of the project's goals, progress, and achievements, ensuring stakeholders are consistently informed about the project's status and impact.

3.5 Presentations

Two types of project presentations will be made available to partners:

- **Short Standard Presentation:** This slide-based presentation is designed to inform a broad audience about the project's objectives and activities.

- **Extended Expert Presentation:** This comprehensive presentation is tailored for a more specialised audience, including professionals, technical experts, researchers, user organisations, and policymakers.

Both presentations will be periodically updated to reflect the latest outcomes and adapted to suit different audiences. They are written in English and distributed to all consortium partners for international use.

3.6 Social Media Presence

The social media strategy for the PLIADES project is focused on leveraging X and LinkedIn, identified as the most suitable platforms for reaching our target audiences. These channels serve as powerful tools for regularly disseminating relevant project information and engaging with specific stakeholder groups.

PLIADES has established profiles on the following social networks:

- **X page:** <https://twitter.com/PLIADESproject>
- **LinkedIn page:** <https://www.linkedin.com/company/pliades-project>

Additionally, a **YouTube channel** has been established to serve as a repository for all project-related videos, enhancing community engagement and visibility of PLIADES activities. All videos will be uploaded to the dedicated channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@PLIADESproject>

By maintaining a robust social media presence, PLIADES aims to foster a dynamic and interactive platform for sharing progress, results, and insights with a broad audience.

The following figures illustrate the home page of PLIADES X page, LinkedIn page and YouTube channel:

Figure 18. PLIADES X page

Figure 19. PLIADES LinkedIn page

Figure 20. PLIADES YouTube channel

3.7 Newsletters

The PLIADES project will publish newsletters every six months, starting from July 2024. These newsletters will be a key communication tool, providing updates on the project's progress and activities to all stakeholders within the partners' networks.

Frequency and Timing:

- **Biannual Updates:** Newsletters will be issued twice a year, ensuring regular communication and engagement with stakeholders.

Content and Focus:

- **Project Updates:** Each newsletter will feature short news items about the project's work, recent progress, and planned activities.
- **Event Reports:** Summaries and reports on participation in conferences, workshops, and other relevant events will be included to highlight the project's outreach and engagement efforts.
- **Upcoming Events:** A news corner will provide information on upcoming events and planned participation, keeping stakeholders informed about future opportunities to engage with the project.

Design and Format:

- The newsletters will be designed to be visually appealing and easy to read, incorporating the PLIADES branding elements such as the project logo and color palette. The format will be adaptable for viewing on various devices, ensuring accessibility for all users.

3.8 Short Videos

Further promotion of the PLIADES project will be achieved through appropriately prepared video material, which will be published regularly. These videos will be designed to summarise the project outcomes and make the project understandable for the public and promote its activities, scope and achieved results.

Videos will be produced and released on a regular schedule to keep the audience engaged and informed about the latest developments and achievements of the PLIADES project.

Types of Videos:

- **Overview Video:** An introductory video outlining the project's goals, objectives, and expected impacts. This video will serve as a comprehensive introduction to the PLIADES project, providing viewers with a clear understanding of its purpose and scope.
- **Content Demonstrations/Workshops:** Videos showcasing demonstrations and workshops related to the project. These will provide practical insights into the project's applications and methodologies, offering a closer look on the PLIADES project.
- **Promo Video of Pilots:** Promotional videos focusing on pilots. These will highlight the specific pilots within the PLIADES project, showcasing their progress, challenges and successes to illustrate the project's practical impact.
- **Webinars:** Recorded webinars featuring experts and stakeholders discussing various aspects of the PLIADES project. These webinars will provide in-depth information and facilitate knowledge sharing, addressing both technical and non-technical audiences.
- **Recorded Presentations at Workshops/ Conferences:** Recordings of presentations given at various workshops and conferences. These videos will capture key presentations and insights shared during these events, allowing a broader audience to benefit from the knowledge exchanged.

3.9 Workshops/ Conferences/ Demonstrations

Engaging with the broader community through conferences, workshops, exhibitions, and demonstrations is a cornerstone of the PLIADES project's dissemination strategy. These events provide invaluable opportunities to showcase the project's innovations, foster collaborations, and gain insights from industry leaders, researchers, and policymakers. By actively participating in and organising such events, PLIADES aims to build a robust network of stakeholders and enhance the visibility and impact of its work.

Organisation and Attendance:

Through the organisation and attendance of conferences and workshops, PLIADES aims to disseminate its outcomes and attract more entities to widen the network and dataspace ecosystem. Results from the project will be showcased at various prominent events, including International Data Week, Gaia-X Summit, EU Industry Days, EOSC Symposium, and AI-on-demand events. Special attention will be given to participation in the European Big Data Value Forum, Data Week Conference (organised by BDVA and EC), and EUH4D DATA FORUM, through both oral and poster presentations. The project aims to organise/ co-organise at least two major events and attend a minimum of 15 relevant conferences and workshops. All partners are encouraged to promote the project within their industrial, research, and community networks to maximise outreach and impact.

Open Access Exhibitions and Demonstration Events:

To broaden the reach of the PLIADES project and engage with a non-specialised audience, open access exhibitions and demonstration events will be organised. These events are designed to make the project's innovations accessible to a diverse audience, providing an engaging and informative experience that highlights the practical applications and benefits of PLIADES. At least one exhibition and two demo days will be organised, targeting over 100 attendees. These events will demonstrate the project's pilots in a lively and lightweight format, making the innovations accessible to a broad audience. Demonstration cases will be deployed by integration partners and showcased in these exhibition activities. The focus will be on presenting innovative business scenarios to end-users, industrial partners, policymakers, and stakeholders.

Onsite Pilot Promotional Demonstrations and Workshops:

Onsite pilot promotional demonstrations and workshops are pivotal for directly engaging with potential users/ customers and stakeholders. These events aim to attract customers, raise awareness about the project's benefits, and disseminate the results of the PLIADES project through practical, hands-on experiences. At least one demonstration per pilot will be conducted, with each pilot hosting at least two workshops. These demonstrations aim to provide direct, hands-on experience with the PLIADES technologies. Feedback from participants will be gathered to refine and improve future demonstrations.

Online and Face-to-Face Training and Webinars:

Online and face-to-face training sessions and webinars will be organised to provide comprehensive and accessible education on the project's technologies and their applications. At least two training sessions or webinars will be conducted. These sessions will demonstrate the system in an instructive and engaging manner. Aiming to reach at least 50 attendees per session, these events will provide comprehensive training to ensure that users can effectively utilise the PLIADES systems.

These integrated efforts and detailed plans are designed to ensure broad engagement, effective dissemination of knowledge, and a lasting impact of the PLIADES project across various sectors and communities.

3.10 Publications

Scientific Publications and Presentations/ Open access reports

Scientific papers will be published in high-impact journals and presented at conferences to share the project's findings with the academic and professional communities, enhancing the project's credibility and impact. The project's scientific results will be published in the international scientific/technical literature, including but not limited to:

- MDPI;
- Intelligent Computing;
- Journal of Information Technology (JIT);
- Digital Health;
- other SAGE journals;
- other IEEE publications;
- EPRI, ASME and ELSEVIER journals;
- as well as in relevant technical literature at national level.

Moreover, in order to follow the standardisation process, a proposal for the data structure will be prepared and submitted to ISO. Each year, the project aims to submit at least one high-quality journal paper.

To complement journal publications, the project will actively participate in key conferences relevant to its areas of expertise. The project targets a minimum of fifteen **conference presentations** annually to share its innovative approaches and findings with a global audience.

Non-scientific reports

The project aims to facilitate industry adoption by publishing insights and case studies in at least one industry magazine annually. This outreach strategy will highlight practical applications and benefits derived from the PLIADES framework, fostering interest and uptake among industry stakeholders.

Project Technical e-Publication

A technical e-publication will be produced to collect relevant results in the form of data and observations from pilot data spaces. This publication will provide comprehensive evidence on the advantages of the developed PLIADES framework, and the lessons learned throughout the project.

3.11 Collaborations

Industry Links and Collaboration

The PLIADES project recognises the importance of fostering synergistic relationships within industry to accelerate the adoption of dataspace and their ecosystems. By establishing strong industry links, the project aims to attract additional partners who can contribute expertise and resources, further enhancing the development and deployment of innovative solutions.

Liaison with EU Projects and Initiatives

To maximise impact and reach, PLIADES will actively liaise with and collaborate with other relevant EU projects and initiatives. This collaborative approach aims to create synergies, complement activities, and amplify dissemination efforts across Europe. Key initiatives and communities that PLIADES will engage with include:

- European Data Spaces Initiative
- Data Spaces Support Centre - DSSC
- International Data Spaces Association - IDSA

- GAIA-X
- SIMPL
- BDVA
- FIWARE
- PrepDSpace4Mobility
- Collaborative Approach

Through these collaborations, PLIADES aims to leverage shared resources, knowledge, and networks to advance its objectives. By aligning with complementary projects and initiatives, PLIADES will enhance the scalability and sustainability of its outcomes, ultimately contributing to the broader European digital transformation agenda.

4 Execution Plan & KPIs

4.1 Rules and Guidelines

The dissemination strategy and activities outlined in the previous sections for PLIADES are designed to utilise a diverse range of communication tools effectively. However, it is crucial to adopt these tools carefully to ensure that the project's dissemination goals are effectively met. Before proceeding with any dissemination activities, PLIADES partners should consider the following checklist to maximise impact and outreach:

Dissemination Checklist:

- **Objective Definition:** Clearly define what is to be disseminated. Is it a key project milestone, a specific deliverable, or important research findings?
- **Target Audience:** Identify the primary and secondary target groups for each dissemination effort, including stakeholders, policymakers, researchers, and the general public.
- **Key Messages:** Determine the core messages to be communicated. Ensure these messages align with project objectives and resonate with the intended audience.
- **Impact Goals:** Outline the desired impact of each dissemination activity. How does this activity contribute to achieving the overarching goals of PLIADES?
- **Communication Tools:** Select the most suitable communication tools for reaching each target group effectively. Adapt the writing and communication style to ensure clarity and relevance to the audience.
- **Length and Accessibility:** Ensure that the communication supports are concise, easy to read, and accessible to all target groups.
- **Acknowledgement of Funding:** Include reference to the European Union's Horizon Europe funding in all dissemination materials as appropriate.
- **Confidentiality Considerations:** Verify if any information needs to adhere to confidentiality rules before dissemination.
- **Contact Information:** Clearly provide contact details and links to the PLIADES project website for further information.
- **Measurement Indicators:** Define specific indicators to measure the success and impact of each dissemination activity, such as reach, engagement metrics, and feedback.

Moreover, the participation of PLIADES partners in future events should align with the following criteria to maximise impact:

- **Scope:** Select events that cover both specialised topics and the core framework of PLIADES, reflecting its multidisciplinary nature.
- **Short-term Impact:** Prioritise scientific events that offer immediate visibility and awareness within the scientific community.
- **Long-term Impact:** Plan for submissions to top journals and selective conferences as the project's scientific results mature, ensuring sustained impact and recognition.

4.2 Communication Tools and KPIs

The following table provides an initial outline of all dissemination channels and activities, along with their corresponding Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and targets.

Table 6. Dissemination channels and activities overview with KPIs and targets

Dissemination Channels and Activities	Objectives	KPIs	Targets
Project Identity and Branding	Establish a recognisable project identity.	Number of branding materials created and distributed.	Logo, colour-space, artboard, graphic visuals
Project Website	Central information point for the project.	Website traffic statistics (unique visitors, page views), registrations, blog interactions.	≥700 visits; >120 registrations; ≥150 blog interactions
Marketing Pack and Promotional Press Kit	Provide promotional materials.	Number of materials created.	Leaflet, poster, slide-presentations, factsheet
Web/Social Content (Blogposts, Articles, white papers)	Increase awareness and engagement.	Frequency of content posts.	Y1: >1/month
			Y2: >2/month
			Y3: >2/month
Social Media (LinkedIn, Twitter)	Increase awareness and engagement.	Number of followers, posts, and interactions.	≥200 followers; ≥150 posts; ≥2000 interactions
Press Releases, Newsletters, and Digital Briefs	Inform stakeholders about key activities and events.	Number of press releases, newsletters, audience reach.	Y1: ≥4
			Y2: ≥6
			Y3: ≥10
Videos (YouTube Channel)	Summarise project outcomes and promote activities.	Number of videos produced, views, and feedback.	1 promo/pilot/tool; total >10 videos
Organisation/ Attendance to Conferences/ Workshops	Share knowledge and engage with stakeholders.	Number of conferences/workshops organised and attended, number of visitors, and speakers.	Organised: ≥2; Attended: ≥15; ≥80 visitors; 10 speakers
Open Access Exhibitions and Demonstration Events	Demonstrate project results to the public and stakeholders.	Number of exhibitions, demo days, and attendees.	≥1 exhibition; ≥2 demo days; ≥100 attendees
Onsite Pilot Promotional	Showcase pilot activities and	Number of demonstrations and workshops per pilot.	≥1 demonstration per pilot; ≥2 workshops per pilot

Demonstrations/ Workshops	engage with stakeholders.		
Online and/or F2F Training/ Webinars	Provide training and disseminate knowledge.	Number of webinars/trainings and attendees.	≥2 webinars/ trainings; ≥50 attendees
Scientific Publications and Presentations/ Open access reports	Share scientific findings and research outcomes.	Number of journals and conference papers published.	≥5 journals; ≥15 conference papers
Non-Scientific Reports	Disseminate information to a broader audience.	Number of industry magazine articles.	≥1 industry magazine
Project Technical e-Publication	Provide detailed project information.	Number of downloads.	<25 = poor; 25-75 = good; >75 = excellent
Industry Links and Synergies	Establish connections with industry for real market implementation.	Number of real market links, adopters, and trials/testers.	≥10 real market links; ≥5 adopters; ≥5 trials/testers
F2F with SMEs and Large Industries/ Companies	Engage directly with industry for feedback and collaboration.	Number of events and appearances.	≥1 event; ≥1 appearance

5 Monitoring

The dissemination manager will regularly remind partners of the dissemination activities they need to carry out, as outlined in the dissemination plan. Specific dissemination campaigns will be organised around key milestones, events, or activities.

Monitoring the performed activities is a crucial aspect of the dissemination plan, aiming to assess the effectiveness of the dissemination efforts. All partners will be required to regularly provide information on what, where, how, and when they disseminated the project activities and results.

Activities monitoring will involve gathering key information, both quantitative data (numbers) and qualitative data (communication impact and results), in line with the targeted KPIs as presented in section 4.2 for each communication tool. Appropriate and suitable templates are available to partners for information gathering (see section 6.5). These templates, along with the communication tools presented in chapter 4, ensure that partners are informed of the exact type of information required when planning their communication activities and facilitate the registration of all necessary data.

6 Appendix

6.1 Deliverable template

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101135988

AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability

Project acronym:	PLIADES
Project name:	AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability
Grant Agreement No:	101135988
Call:	HORIZON-CL4-2023-DATA-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2023-DATA-01-02
Type of action:	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Start of project:	01/01/2024

Deliverable

Deliverable title	
--------------------------	--

Work Package:	
Task:	
Lead Beneficiary:	
Due Date:	
Submission Date:	
Deliverable Status:	
Deliverable Type:	
Dissemination Level:	

GA #101135988

Authors

Surname	First Name	Beneficiary

Reviewers

Surname	First Name	Beneficiary

Version History

Version	Date	Modifications made by

Disclaimer

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6.2 Presentation template

AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability

Speaker's name
Speakers' organisation
Date and place

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101135988

Click to add title

- Edit Master text styles

Footer 2

Thank you for your attention!

Any Questions?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101135988

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[@PLIADESproject](https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC...)

[pliades-project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/pliades-project)

6.3 1st Press Release - Project Overview

AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces
Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability

PRESS RELEASE

Revolutionising Data Utilisation Across Sectors

The PLIADES project

17 May 2024: A team of researchers led by the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas/ Information Technologies Institute (Greece), embarked on a ground-breaking journey with the launch of the PLIADES project. Funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme with a budget of €9 million, **PLIADES (AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimisation and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability)** aims to redefine how data is utilised across sectors, from mobility to healthcare, manufacturing to energy, and beyond.

The primary mission of PLIADES is to introduce an advanced AI-enabled framework for Full Data Lifecycles Optimisation and Data Spaces Integration. This visionary project envisions a future where diverse sectors are seamlessly interconnected, fostering efficiency and interoperability. By providing cutting-edge data and services, PLIADES aims to drive advancements in Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM), Advanced Driver Assistance & Autonomous Driving (ADAS/ AD), and Human-Robot Interaction (HRI).

Under the coordination of Dr. Dimitrios Giakoumis (CERTH-ITI), the PLIADES project brings together a consortium of twenty-seven* partners from 10 EU Member States and Switzerland. This diverse consortium includes 12 Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs), 10 Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), and 5 Non-Profit Organisations (NPOs).

The project seeks to research and develop novel models, abstractions, and methods for environmentally friendly, context- and human-factors-aware creation of vast amounts of data for mobility, green deal, energy, industrial, and healthcare dataspace. Moreover, PLIADES aims to advance data privacy, security, trustworthiness, and sovereignty, enabling data owners to safely determine how their information is collected, stored and used. Additionally, PLIADES seeks to promote advanced data decentralisation and further advance AI-boosted brokers, to generate advanced Data Space connectors to extend the scope of data space interoperability, integrating full data life cycles into existing data reference architectures, such as the IDS Reference Architecture Model. Furthermore, PLIADES is committed to facilitating novel data processing and analytics services to ensure data privacy, trustworthiness, security, resilience, reuse, and disposal.

PLIADES will deploy its proposed framework in six use cases spanning transportation, energy, manufacturing, healthcare, and the green deal sectors. These use cases will leverage different

AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability

types of data to drive innovations in areas such as smart vehicles, predictive maintenance, personalised healthcare services, and more, solving critical problems and improving everyday life.

***Consortium members include:**

Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas CERTH (Greece), I4byDesign Competence Center Private Company (Greece), Atlantis Engineering SA (Greece), Vicomtech (Spain), Eurecat (Spain), Energy@Work (Italy), FinEst Centre for Smart Cities, TallTech (Estonia), Innovaia (Spain) Tecnalia (Spain), denn Industrias Puigjaner (Spain), Blue Ocean Robotics (Denmark), Czech Technical University in Prague (Czech Republic), Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt (Germany), ZERO GmbH (Germany), Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (Spain), Mondragon Goi Eskola Politeknikoa Jose Maria Arizmendiarieta, S.Coop (Spain), KU Leuven, Mecha(tro)nic System Dynamics (LMSD) research group (Belgium), Ceit - Centro de Estudios e Investigaciones Técnicas (Spain), IDSA - International Data Spaces e.V. (Germany), TNO - Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (Netherlands), CIC bioGUNE - Asociación Centro de Investigación Cooperativa en Biociencias (Spain), BasqueCCAM - Asociación Centro Vasco de Movilidad Conectada, Cooperativa y Autónoma (Spain), AVL List GmbH (Austria), White Research (Brussels), Hypertech S.A. (Greece), Libattion AG (Switzerland), Sipbb - Switzerland Innovation Park Biel/ Bienne AG (Switzerland)

For more information about PLIADES and its ground-breaking initiatives, please visit: <https://www.pliades-project.eu/>

Follow us on X via [@PLIADESproject](#) and on LinkedIn via [pliades-project](#)

Subscribe to our YouTube channel [here](#).

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Available online:

<https://www.pliades-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/PLIADES-Press-Release-2024.05.17-Project-Overview.pdf>

6.4 General Audience Leaflet

Target Values

Scientific: Research and development of innovative tools and standards

- that address critical challenges in data creation, storage, ownership, discovery, and disposal across diverse data spaces.

Societal: Produce greener data and enhanced services and products

- using advanced yet eco-friendly data processing methods for data generation,
- and improve everyday life through personalised healthcare products, smart vehicles, etc.

Economic/ Technological: The deployment of the PLIADES framework aims to:

- reduce resource requirements for data acquisition,
- improve technological solutions and promote advancements across multiple industries, through the utilisation of vast amounts of high-quality data,
- enable synergies between multiple data spaces for development of innovative technologies.

Who are we?

27 Partners across 10 EU Member States & Switzerland
 Consortium Breakdown: 12 RTOs, 10 SMEs, 5 NPOs

Project timeline

Start Date: January 1st, 2024
End Date: June 30th, 2027 (42 months)

Important Milestones:

- Definition of system architecture (2024)
- Preliminary deployment of framework (2026)
- Launch of PLIADES data spaces (2026)
- Pilot testing and evaluation (2027)

AI-Enabled Data Lifecycles Optimization and Data Spaces Integration for Increased Efficiency and Interoperability

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Follow us on:

Project Coordinator:
 Dr. Dimitrios Giakoumis
 Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH), Information Technologies Institute (ITI)

Mission

PLIADES stands for an advanced AI-enabled framework for Full Data Lifecycles Optimisation and Data Spaces Integration. Our mission is to revolutionize how data is utilised across various sectors, from mobility to healthcare, manufacturing to energy, and beyond.

PLIADES envisions a future where diverse sectors are seamlessly interconnected, enhancing efficiency and interoperability.

We aim to provide cutting-edge data and services that drive advancements in Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM), Advanced Driver Assistance & Autonomous Driving (ADAS/AD), and Human-Robot Interaction (HRI).

Objectives

The specific objectives of PLIADES are to:

- Research and develop novel models, abstractions, and methods for environmentally friendly, context- and human-factors-aware creation of vast amounts of data for mobility, green deal, energy, industrial and healthcare dataspaces.
- Advance data privacy, security, trustworthiness and sovereignty, enabling data owners to safely determine how their information is collected, stored and used.
- Promote advanced data decentralisation and further advance AI-boostered brokers.
- Generate advanced Data Spaces connectors to extend the scope of data spaces interoperability, encompassing full data life cycles into existing data reference architectures.
- Facilitate novel data processing and analytics services to ensure data privacy, trustworthiness, security, resilience, re-use and disposal.
- Deploy the proposed framework in diverse use cases, focusing on transportation, energy, manufacturing, healthcare and green deal sectors.
- Develop new business models that promote data sharing and re-use and establish synergies with other EU initiatives.

Use cases

PLIADES outcomes will utilise different types of data spanning six use cases, focusing on diverse dataspace, such as:

- data from smart vehicles to improve their ADAS/AD & CCAM functions and energy management (mobility dataspace),
- patient/doctor HRI data to improve service robots' HRI effectiveness and patient data to improve diagnostic & prognostic clinical models for personalised medicine services (healthcare dataspace),
- manufacturing data to improve zero-waste manufacturing, predictive maintenance and HRI (industrial dataspace).

Available online:

<https://www.pliades-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/PLIADES-Brochure.pdf>

6.5 Dissemination Activities Report (every 3 months)

Dissemination Activities

No	Type of activities ¹	Title	Attended/Foreseen	Date	Place	Type of Audience ('multiple choices' is possible) ²	Size of audience	Countries addressed	Web links	Comments

¹ Publications, Conferences, Workshops, Web, Press releases, Flyers, Articles published in the popular press, Videos, Media briefings, Presentations, Exhibitions, Thesis, Interviews, Films, TV clips, Posters, Other

² Scientific Community (higher education, Research), Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers, Medias

Scientific Publications

No	Title	Attended/ Foreseen	Authors	Title of the Journal/ Proc./ Book	Number, date or frequency of the Journal/ Proc./ Book	Is Peer- reviewed	Publisher	Place of publication	Year of publication	Relevant Pages	Length of the Embargo, if any (months)	Permanent identifiers (if available) ¹	Is this publication available in Open- Access, or will it be made available? ²	Is this a joint public/private publication? ³

¹ A permanent identifier should be a persistent link to the published version full text if open access or abstract if article is pay per view) or to the final manuscript accepted for publication (link to article in repository).

² Open Access is defined as free of charge access for anyone via Internet. Please answer "yes" if the open access to the publication is already established; if the embargo period for open access is not yet over but you intend to establish open access afterwards, indicate the estimated date when open access will be established.

³ Both the joint publications coming from public and private project participants as well as from private/ public project participants with public/ private organisations outside the consortium (as long as they are related to the funded project) should be reported.